

Harnessing Solar Energy for Sustainable Agriculture among Farmers in Haryana

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The present study examined the historical growth, adoption and socio-economic impact of solar energy technologies among farmers in Haryana. Historically, Haryana agriculture largely depended on diesel and electricity-operated irrigation systems, leading to rising production costs and environmental degradation. With the introduction of renewable energy policies and subsidy schemes such as PM-KUSUM, solar technology emerged as a sustainable alternative in agriculture. The study was conducted on 240 farmers selected from Sirsa, Fatehabad and Hisar districts through multistage random sampling. The findings revealed that majority of the farmers possessed high knowledge (43.75%) and high adoption (35.00%) regarding solar energy systems. Solar energy significantly reduced dependence on conventional electricity (75.83%), lowered diesel and irrigation costs, improved farm income and enhanced household assets and quality of life. Education, landholding, income, mass media exposure and socio-economic status were significantly associated with adoption and knowledge levels. However, lack of trained technicians, procedural delays in subsidy schemes and inadequate service support were major constraints faced by farmers. The study concluded that solar energy has positively transformed the socio-economic conditions of farming families and promoted sustainable agricultural development in Haryana. The study suggests strengthening extension services, simplifying subsidy procedures, improving technical guidance and increasing awareness programmes to encourage wider adoption of solar technologies in rural areas.

Keywords: Nature, knowledge and adoption of solar energy, socio-economic factors, socio-economic impact

The rapid depletion of conventional energy resources and increasing environmental degradation have compelled nations across the globe to shift towards sustainable and renewable sources of energy. In the agricultural sector, energy plays a vital role in irrigation, mechanization and overall farm productivity. In India, agriculture remains highly dependent on electricity and diesel-operated pumps, which not only increase production costs but also contribute to environmental pollution and carbon emissions. Solar energy has emerged as one of the most promising renewable energy alternatives due to its eco-friendly nature, economic viability and long-term sustainability. Haryana, being an agriculturally advanced state, has witnessed a growing adoption of solar energy technologies in recent years, particularly through government subsidy programmes promoting solar pumps and solar-based irrigation systems. The increasing acceptance of solar technology among farmers reflects changing patterns of rural development, technological modernization and sustainable agricultural practices.

From a sociological perspective, the adoption of solar energy in agriculture is not merely a technological phenomenon but also a

process deeply influenced by socio-economic conditions, social awareness, educational background, landholding patterns, family structure and access to institutional support. Farmers' attitudes towards renewable energy technologies are shaped by their economic capabilities, social participation, exposure to mass media and interaction with extension agencies. Solar energy adoption has the potential to transform rural society by reducing dependency on conventional electricity, lowering irrigation costs, improving agricultural productivity and enhancing the socio-economic status of farming families. It also contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting clean energy use in rural communities. Studies have indicated that renewable energy technologies significantly improve farmers' income, strengthen livelihood security and promote sustainable rural development (Sharma & Singh, 2020; Kumar et al., 2021). Moreover, government initiatives such as PM-KUSUM have accelerated the diffusion of solar technologies among Indian farmers by providing financial assistance and institutional support (MNRE, 2022).

Despite the growing popularity of solar energy systems, several challenges continue to affect their effective adoption and utilization among farmers, particularly in rural areas. Lack of technical knowledge, inadequate service support, high installation costs, limited access to trained technicians and procedural difficulties in availing subsidies remain major barriers to the widespread diffusion of solar technology. In Haryana, where agriculture forms the backbone of the rural economy, understanding the socio-economic impact of solar energy adoption becomes essential for designing effective rural development and energy policies. Therefore, the present study entitled "Harnessing Solar Energy for Sustainable Agriculture in Haryana" was undertaken to examine the knowledge and adoption level of solar energy among farmers, analyze the socio-

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economic factors associated with its adoption and assess its social and economic impact on farming households. The study also attempts to identify the constraints faced by farmers in adopting solar energy technologies for agricultural purposes. In light of the above statements, the paper attempts to answer the following research questions:

Research Questions

- To assess the nature, extent, knowledge and adoption of solar energy for agriculture in Haryana
- To delineate the socio-economic factors affecting with knowledge and adoption of solar energy
- To examine the socio-economic impact of solar energy on farmers along with constraints.

Method

Participants

The present study was conducted in three agriculturally important districts of Haryana namely Sirsa, Fatehabad and Hisar to examine the socio-economic impact of solar energy adoption in agriculture among farmers. A multistage sampling technique was employed for the selection of respondents. Initially, the districts were selected purposively due to the increasing adoption of solar energy systems in agriculture. Thereafter, villages namely Ludhesar, Rupavas and Rupana from Sirsa district; Matana, Bhigad, Dhani Miyan Khan, Dharnia, Samain and Kanhari from Fatehabad district; and Prabhuwala, Shahpur, Charnod and Saharwa from Hisar district were selected for the study. From these villages, a total of 240 farmers were selected randomly, comprising 80 farmers from each district.

Measure

The study utilized a comprehensive interview schedule specifically designed in accordance with the objectives of the research. The schedule included items related to socio-economic characteristics, knowledge level regarding solar energy, adoption practices, reasons for adoption, socio-economic impact and constraints faced by farmers in using solar energy systems in agriculture. Knowledge and adoption levels were measured using structured statements with response categories such as fully knowledgeable, partially knowledgeable and no knowledge as well as fully adopted, moderately adopted and not adopted. Socio-economic impact was assessed through social and economic dimensions including quality of life, household assets, irrigation facilities, farm income, reduction in electricity dependency and employment opportunities. Weighted Mean Score (WMS) and Total Weighted Score (TWS) techniques were employed to assess the relative importance of different dimensions and statements.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques suitable for sociological and social science research. Frequency and percentage analysis were employed to describe the distribution patterns of socio-economic variables and adoption characteristics among farmers. To examine the relative importance and ranking of different statements related to knowledge, adoption, impact and constraints, Total Weighted Score (TWS), Weighted Mean Score (WMS), rank order and overall mean score were

calculated. Further, chi-square (χ^2) tests were applied to determine the association between socio-economic variables and the levels of knowledge and adoption of solar energy systems among farmers.

Procedure

Primary data were collected personally from the selected farmers through face-to-face interviews using interview schedule. The investigators visited the selected villages and established rapport with the respondents to obtain accurate and reliable information regarding their experiences with solar energy systems. The collected information was classified, coded and tabulated systematically to facilitate detailed sociological analysis and interpretation.

Results and Discussion

Contextual Matrix of Farmers

Table 1 presents the age-wise distribution of 240 farmers across three districts namely Sirsa, Fatehabad and Hisar with 80 farmers from each district. The maximum number of farmers (47.50%) hailed from 30-45 years age group and 4560 years group (30.41%), while 22.09 per cent farmers were above 60 years of age group. District-wise, both Hisar and Fatehabad had the highest proportion of young farmers (56.25% & 43.75%), respectively. The overall average age of the farmers across all districts was 48.68 years. Caste-wise data reveals that more than half of the farmers (52.50%) belonged to General Category and Backward Classes (36.25%). More than one-fourth of farmers (27.92%) educated up to senior secondary school level followed by secondary (24.58%) and middle (16.67%). Even a substantial chunk of 7.50 per cent were illiterate. Further, analysis reveals that average education of farmers was found up to 9.30 class across all districts. All farmers from the field of the study were engaged in farming occupation. A perusal of data reveals that more than half of the farmers (57.08%) were not engaged in any subsidiary occupation. More than one-fourth of the farmers (25.84%) were engaged in business and jobs activities as subsidiary occupation and small-scale enterprise (17.08%).

The Table 1 outlines that nearly one-third of the farmers (31.26%) had small landholdings followed by marginal (29.16%) and semi-medium (28.75%). The average size of landholding was found 6.64 acres in Sirsa district followed by Fatehabad 5.39 acres and Hisar 4.73 acres. The overall average size of landholding was found 5.58 acres across all districts. More than half of the farmers (56.67%) maintained a joint family, while the rest had a nuclear family (43.33%). More than half of the farmers (52.92%) had 5-8 members in their families and up to 4 members (28.33%). The table 1 presents that nearly one-third of the farmers (30.42%) earned annual income from Rs. 2,00,001-3,00,000/- and Rs. 3,00,001-4,00,000/- (27.08%), respectively. Further, table highlights that average annual income was found Rs. 3,06,250/- in Sirsa district and Fatehabad Rs. 2,81,250/-. The overall average annual income was found Rs. 3,05,333/- across all districts. Table 1 illustrates that nearly half of the farmers (47.50%) did not participate in any social organization. Even 28.75 per cent farmers participated more than one social organization. More than half of the farmers (50.84%) had low exposure to mass-media across all districts. It was also found that nearly two-fifth of the farmers (38.34%) had low level of socio-economic status followed by medium (35.41%) and high (26.25%).

Table 1
Contextual Matrix of Farmers (n=240)

Socio-economic variables	Districts			Total (n=240)
	Sirsa (n=80)	Fatehabad (n=80)	Hisar (n=80)	
Age group				
30-45 years	34 (42.50)	35 (43.75)	45 (56.25)	114 (47.50)
45-60 years	24 (30.00)	27 (33.75)	22 (27.50)	73 (30.41)
Above 60 years	22 (27.50)	18 (22.50)	13 (16.25)	53 (22.09)
Average age	50.25	49.31	46.50	48.68
Caste				
General	46 (57.50)	30 (37.50)	50 (62.50)	126 (52.50)
Backward	28 (35.00)	40 (50.00)	19 (23.75)	87 (36.25)
Scheduled	6 (07.50)	10 (12.50)	11 (13.75)	27 (11.25)
Level of education				
Illiterate	5 (06.25)	8 (10.00)	5 (06.25)	18 (07.50)
Primary school	13 (16.25)	10 (12.50)	9 (11.25)	32 (13.33)
Middle school	18 (22.50)	13 (16.25)	9 (11.25)	40 (16.67)
Secondary school	14 (17.50)	19 (23.75)	26 (32.50)	59 (24.58)
Senior secondary school	25 (31.25)	24 (30.00)	18 (22.50)	67 (27.92)
Graduation or above	5 (06.25)	6 (07.50)	13 (16.25)	24 (10.00)
Average of education	9.05	9.025	9.85	9.30
Subsidiary occupation				
No occupation	52 (65.00)	50 (62.50)	35 (43.75)	137 (57.08)
Business and jobs	19 (23.75)	20 (25.00)	23 (28.75)	62 (25.84)
Small-scale enterprise	9 (11.25)	10 (12.50)	22 (27.50)	41 (17.08)
Size of landholding (acre)				
Marginal (up to 2.5)	17 (21.25)	21 (26.25)	32 (40.00)	70 (29.16)
Small (2.5- 5.0)	22 (27.50)	34 (42.50)	19 (23.75)	75 (31.26)
Semi-medium (5.0-10.0)	29 (36.25)	16 (20.00)	24 (30.00)	69 (28.75)
Medium (10.0-25.0)	12 (15.00)	9 (11.25)	5 (06.25)	26 (10.83)
Average size of landholding (acres)	6.64	5.39	4.73	5.58
Type of family				
Nuclear	35 (43.75)	38 (47.50)	31 (38.75)	104 (43.33)
Joint	45 (56.25)	42 (52.50)	49 (61.25)	136 (56.67)
Size of family				
Up to 4 members	20 (25.00)	30 (37.50)	28 (35.00)	68 (28.33)
5-8 members	41 (51.25)	35 (43.75)	41 (51.25)	127 (52.92)
Above 8 members	19 (23.75)	15 (18.75)	11 (13.75)	45 (18.75)
Annual family income (Rs.)				
1,00,000-2,00,000/-	15 (18.75)	22 (27.50)	27 (33.75)	64 (26.66)
2,00,001-3,00,000/-	22 (27.50)	24 (30.00)	27 (33.75)	73 (30.42)
3,00,001-4,00,000/-	26 (32.50)	21 (26.25)	18 (22.50)	65 (27.08)
Above 4,00,000/-	17 (21.25)	13 (16.25)	8 (10.00)	38 (15.84)
Average annual income	3,06,250	2,81,250	2,58,750	2,82,083.33
Social participation				
No participation	43 (53.75)	39 (48.75)	32 (40.00)	114 (47.50)
Member of one organisation	16 (20.00)	19 (23.75)	22 (27.50)	57 (23.75)
Member of more than one organisation	21 (26.25)	22 (27.50)	26 (32.50)	69 (28.75)
Mass media exposure				
Low (up to 10)	37 (46.25)	35 (43.75)	50 (62.50)	122 (50.84)
Medium (10-18)	21 (26.25)	25 (31.25)	19 (23.75)	65 (27.08)
High (18-24)	22 (27.50)	20 (25.00)	11 (13.75)	53 (22.08)
Socio-economic status				
Low (12-18)	26 (32.50)	27 (33.75)	39 (48.75)	92 (38.34)
Medium (18-24)	29 (36.25)	30 (37.50)	26 (32.50)	85 (35.41)
High (24-30)	25 (31.25)	23 (28.75)	15 (18.75)	63 (26.25)

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage

Table 2*Various Features of Solar Energy System in Agriculture (n=240)*

Year of Initiation of Solar Energy System	Frequency	Percentage
2019-20	48	20.00
2021-22	85	35.42
2023-24	107	44.58
Number of installed solar energy systems		
Single	202	84.17
Double	38	15.83
Type of solar energy system		
340 watts	128	53.33
540 watts	112	46.67
Subsidy availed on solar energy system		
75.00% subsidy	240	100.00

Solar Energy System in Agriculture

Table 2 presents main attributes of solar energy system adoption among farmers. Maximum number of the farmers (44.58%) installed the solar systems at their field in 2023-24 followed by 2021-22 (35.42%) and 2019-20 (20.00%). Regarding system installation, the overwhelming majority of the farmers (84.17%) installed single solar pump, while 15.83% had double installations. In terms of capacity, 53.33 per cent farmers reported using 340W systems, whereas 46.67 per cent used 540W systems. Notably, 100 per cent farmers availed the 75.00% government subsidy. The present findings are supported by Patel and Kumar (2021) who reported that majority of farmers adopted solar pump systems during recent years

due to increasing government subsidies and rising diesel costs, while most beneficiaries preferred single solar pump installations for irrigation purposes.

Knowledge of Solar Energy among Farmers

Table 3 presents the distribution of farmers' knowledge regarding solar energy use in agriculture across Sirsa, Fatehabad, and Hisar districts of Haryana. The data reveal that majority of farmers possess a high level of awareness about the core benefit of solar pumps in saving electricity, with 80.42% reporting full knowledge (Rank I) followed by familiarity with the usage patterns of solar systems (63.33%, Rank II) and understanding of their environmental benefits (46.66%, Rank III). Moderate knowledge was observed in areas such as solar performance during cloudy days (39.16%) and government subsidy provisions (43.33%). The least understood areas are the installation costs of solar systems (Rank IX) followed by separation of solar and electric pump functions (Rank X) and the generation of electricity through solar pumps (Rank XI). The overall weighted mean score was 2.21, indicating a moderate level of knowledge among farmers. The findings of the present study are supported by Verma and Singh (2020) who reported that farmers possessed comparatively higher knowledge regarding electricity saving, environmental advantages and operational use of solar pumps, whereas awareness related to installation cost, technical functioning and subsidy procedures remained comparatively low. The study further concluded that extension contact and exposure to renewable energy programmes significantly influenced farmers' knowledge regarding solar energy technologies in agriculture.

Table 3*Knowledge of Solar Energy among Farmers Regarding Use in Agriculture (n=240)*

Statements of knowledge	Level of knowledge			TWS	WMS	Rank
	Fully knowledge	Partial knowledge	No knowledge			
Solar pumps save electricity	193 (80.42)	32 (13.33)	15 (6.25)	658	2.74*	I
Solar system usages pattern	152 (63.33)	59 (24.58)	29 (12.08)	603	2.51*	II
Environmental benefits of solar energy	112 (46.66)	75 (31.25)	51 (21.25)	537	2.24*	III
Knowledge of solar during cloudy days	94 (39.16)	93 (38.75)	53 (22.08)	521	2.17	IV
Government subsidies for solar equipment	104 (43.33)	71 (29.58)	65 (27.08)	519	2.16	V
Knowledge of solar pump systems	88 (36.67)	98 (40.83)	54 (22.50)	514	2.14	VI
Familiarity with repair and maintenance procedures	85 (35.42)	92 (38.33)	63 (26.25)	502	2.09	VII
Formalities for installation of solar energy	95 (39.58)	93 (38.75)	52 (21.66)	512	2.13	VIII
Installation charges of solar energy system	68 (28.33)	115 (47.92)	57 (23.75)	491	2.04	IX
Separating solar from electric pumps	89 (37.08)	72 (30.00)	79 (32.91)	490	2.04	X
Generating electricity through solar pumps	79 (32.92)	88 (36.66)	73 (30.41)	486	2.02	XI
Overall Mean Score: 2.21						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Knowledge of Solar Energy

Table 4 presents the level of knowledge of solar energy among farmers. The data show that maximum number of the farmers (43.75%) possessed high knowledge about solar energy penal in agriculture followed by moderate level of knowledge (33.75%) and low knowledge category (22.50%).

Table 4*Level of Knowledge of Solar Energy among Farmers (n=240)*

Level of Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Low (10-18)	54	22.50
Moderate (18-26)	81	33.75
High (26-34)	105	43.75
Total	240	100.00

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Knowledge of Solar Energy among Farmers

Table 5 presents that various socio-economic variable associated with knowledge of farmers. In contrast, subsidiary occupation, types of family, social participation and mass media exposure of the farmers were not significantly associated with knowledge of farmers. Age was found highly significantly associated with knowledge of solar energy system among farmers. Further, analysis reveals that more than three-fifth of the farmers (62.29%) belonged to 30-45 years age group had high level of knowledge. Contrary to that 43.40 per cent farmers belonged above 60 years age group had low level of knowledge. Caste was found highly significantly associated with knowledge of solar energy system among farmers. It was also found that half of the farmers (50.00%) who belonged to general category had high level of knowledge. Contrary to that 37.04 per cent farmers who belonged to Scheduled Caste had low level of knowledge. Education was found highly significantly associated with knowledge of farmers about solar energy penal. In this regard, nearly three-fourth of the farmers (74.62%) who were educated up to senior secondary school had high level of knowledge. In contrast, 50.00 per cent farmers who were illiterate had moderate level of

knowledge of solar energy system.

Table 5 presents that highly Significantly association was found between landholding and knowledge of farmers. Further, perusal data reveal that more than three-fifth of the farmers (62.68%) hailed small landholding had high level of knowledge. On the other hand, 38.57 per cent farmers hailed marginal landholding had low level of knowledge. Highly Significantly association was found between size of family and knowledge of farmers. Further, data show that more than half of the farmers (51.19%) related to 5-8 members in the family had high level of knowledge. Contrary to that 40.00 per cent farmers who were belonged to above 8 members had low level of knowledge. Highly significantly association was found between annual family income and knowledge of farmers. Further, table illustrates that nearly two-third of the farmers (65.80%) who earned above Rs. 4,00, 000/- had high level of knowledge. In contrast, maximum number of the farmers (43.75%) who earned Rs. 1,00, 000 to 2,00,000/- had low level of knowledge. Socio-economic status and knowledge of farmers about solar energy system was found highly significantly associated. Further, results highlight that 55.56 per cent farmers related to high level of socio-economic status had high level of knowledge. In comparison, 38.82 per cent farmers related to medium socio-economic status had moderate level of knowledge.

Table 5

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Knowledge of Solar Energy (n=240)

Socio-economic variables	Level of knowledge			Total
	Low	Moderate	High	
Age group 30-45 years	11(09.64)	32(28.07)	71(62.29)	114(47.50)
45-60 years	20(27.39)	31(42.46)	22(30.14)	73(30.41)
Above 60 years	23(43.40)	18(33.96)	12(22.64)	53(22.09)
Total	54(22.50)	81(33.75)	105(43.75)	240 (100)
df = 4		C= 0.376		χ^2 Cal=39.60**
Caste				
General	16(12.70)	47(37.30)	63(50.00)	126(52.50)
Backward	28(32.19)	26(29.88)	33(37.93)	87(36.25)
Scheduled	10(37.04)	8(29.62)	9(33.34)	27(11.25)
df = 4		C= 0.243		χ^2 Cal=15.00**
Level of education				
Illiterate	5(27.78)	9(50.00)	4(22.22)	18(07.50)
Primary school	10(31.25)	13(40.62)	9(28.13)	32(13.35)
Middle school	8(20.00)	15(37.50)	17(42.50)	40(16.66)
Secondary school	13(22.04)	27(45.76)	19(32.20)	59(24.58)
Senior secondary school	9(13.44)	8(11.94)	50(74.62)	67(27.91)
Graduation or above	9(37.50)	9(37.50)	6(25.00)	24(10.00)
df = 10		C= 0.387		χ^2 Cal=42.39**
Subsidiary occupation				
No occupation	32(23.36)	43(31.38)	62(45.26)	137(57.08)
Business and jobs	12(19.35)	24(38.70)	26(41.95)	62(25.84)
Small scale enterprise	10(24.40)	14(34.14)	17(41.46)	41(17.08)
df = 4		C= 0.071		χ^2 Cal=1.23
Size of land holding (acre)				
Marginal (up to 2.5)	27(38.57)	30(42.85)	13(18.57)	70(29.17)
Small (2.5- 5.0)	8(10.66)	20(26.66)	47(62.68)	75(31.25)
Semi-medium (5.0-10.0)	14(20.28)	23(33.34)	32(36.38)	69(28.75)
Medium (10.0-25.0)	5(19.23)	8(30.77)	13(50.00)	26(10.83)
df = 6		C= 0.345		χ^2 Cal=32.50**

Type of family				
Nuclear	28(26.93)	36(34.61)	40(38.46)	104(43.34)
Joint	26(19.12)	45(33.08)	65(47.80)	136(56.66)
df = 2		C= 0.108		χ^2 Cal=2.81
Size of family				
Up to 4 members	23(33.82)	20(29.41)	25(36.77)	68(28.34)
5-8 members	13(10.23)	49(38.58)	65(51.19)	127(52.91)
Above 8 members	18(40.00)	12(26.67)	15(33.33)	45(18.75)
df = 4		C= 0.301		χ^2 Cal=23.89**
Annual family income (Rs.)				
1,00,000-2,00,000/-	21(32.82)	28(43.75)	15(23.43)	64(26.67)
2,00,000-3,00,000/-	17(23.28)	28(38.36)	28(38.36)	73(30.42)
3,00,001-4,00,000/-	11(16.93)	17(26.15)	37(56.92)	65(27.08)
Above 4,00,000/-	5(13.15)	8(21.05)	25(65.80)	38(15.83)
df = 6		C= 0.302		χ^2 Cal=24.01**
Social participation (membership)				
No participation	28(24.56)	34(29.82)	52(45.62)	114(47.50)
One organisation	12(21.05)	28(49.12)	17(29.83)	57(23.75)
More than one organisation	14(20.28)	19(27.54)	36(52.18)	69(28.75)
df = 4		C= 0.195		χ^2 Cal=9.45
Mass media exposure				
Low (up to 10)	32(26.23)	36(29.50)	54(44.27)	122(50.83)
Medium (10-18)	14(21.53)	28(43.07)	23(35.40)	65(27.09)
High (18-24)	8(15.10)	17(32.08)	28(52.82)	53(22.08)
df = 4		C= 0.162		χ^2 Cal=6.48
Socio-economic status				
Low (12-18)	12(13.04)	30(32.60)	50(54.36)	92(38.34)
Medium (18-24)	32(37.64)	33(38.82)	20(23.52)	85(35.41)
High (24-30)	10(15.87)	18(28.57)	35(55.56)	63(26.25)
df = 4		C= 0.318		χ^2 Cal=27.05**

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Significant at 5% level of significance, **Highly significant at 1% level of significance

Figure 1

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Knowledge of Solar Energy Adoption Level of Solar Energy Practices

Adoption of Solar Energy in Agriculture

Table 6 highlights the adoption level of solar energy practices in agriculture among farmers. More than three-fifth of the farmers (62.50%) fully adopted the practice of regular maintenance and monitoring of solar equipment (Rank I) and recommending solar

technology to others (Rank II), respectively. A small percentage of farmers (11.67%) adopted practices the upgrading or expanding solar systems post-installation (Rank VIII) and technical guidance after adoption (Rank VIII), respectively. The overall weighted mean score was 2.04 indicating a moderate level of adoption among farmers. The findings are in conformity with the study conducted by Kumar and Chahal (2021) who reported that majority of farmers regularly maintained solar equipment and expressed positive attitudes towards recommending solar technology to fellow farmers due to reduced irrigation costs and reliable energy supply. However, adoption of advanced practices such as system upgradation and seeking technical guidance remained comparatively low because of financial and technical constraints faced by rural farmers.

Adoption of Solar Energy

Table 7 presents the level of adoption of solar energy penal among farmers. The data show that more than one-third of the farmers (35.00%) possessed high adoption about solar energy penal in agriculture followed by moderate level of adoption (34.58%) and low adoption category (30.42%).

Table 6
Adoption of Solar Energy in Agriculture by Farmers (n=240)

Statements of adoption	Level of adoption			TWS	WMS	Rank
	Fully adopted	Moderately adopted	Not Adopted			
Regularly maintain and monitor solar equipment	150 (62.50)	62 (25.83)	28 (11.67)	602	2.50*	I
Recommendation of solar technology to other farmers	126 (52.50)	62 (25.83)	52 (21.67)	554	2.30*	II
Utilization pattern of solar energy for more than one agricultural purpose (e.g., irrigation, lighting, storage)	105 (43.75)	87 (36.25)	48 (20.00)	537	2.23*	III
Fully integrated solar systems into farming operations	98 (40.83)	45 (19.17)	96 (40.00)	482	2.01	IV
Formal training of solar energy technology before adoption	67 (27.91)	93 (38.75)	80 (33.34)	467	1.94	V
Replacement of traditional energy sources with solar power	42 (17.50)	135 (56.25)	63 (26.25)	459	1.91	VI
Technical guidance of solar energy technology after adoption	58 (24.17)	98 (40.83)	84 (35.00)	454	1.89	VII
Upgraded or expanded my solar system since initial adoption	28 (11.67)	79 (32.91)	133 (55.42)	375	1.56	VIII
Overall Mean Score: 2.04						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Table 7
Level of Adoption of Solar Energy among Farmers (n=240)

Level of adoption	Frequency	Percentage
Low (8-15)	73	30.42
Moderate (15-22)	83	34.58
High (22-29)	84	35.00
Total	240	100.00

Figure 2
Level of Adoption of Solar Energy among Farmers

Socio-economic Variables and Adoption of Solar Energy

Table 8 presents that various socio-economic variable associated with adoption of solar energy system among farmers. In contrast, age, caste, subsidiary occupation and social participation of farmers were not significantly associated with adoption of solar energy system among farmers. Education was found significantly associated with adoption of solar energy system among farmers. In this regard, maximum number of the farmers (47.77%) who were

educated up to senior secondary school had high level of adoption. In contrast, 55.56 per cent farmers who were illiterate had low level of adoption. Table 8 presents that highly Significant association was found between landholding and adoption of solar energy system. Further, perusal data reveal that half of the farmers (50.00%) who hailed semi-medium landholding had high level of adoption. On the other hand, 42.85 per cent farmers who were landless had low level of adoption. Highly Significant association was found between types of family and adoption of solar energy system. Further, data show that maximum number of the farmers (44.85%) belonged to joint family had moderate level of adoption. Contrary to that 43.28 per cent farmers belonged to nuclear family had low level of adoption.

Highly Significant association was found between size of family and adoption of solar energy system. Further, data show that maximum number of the farmers (48.81%) belonged 5-8 members in the family had moderate level of adoption. Contrary to that 44.13 per cent farmers who were belonged to up to 4 members had low level of adoption. Highly significantly association was found between annual family income and adoption of solar energy system. Further, table illustrates that maximum number of the farmers (47.37%) who earned above Rs. 4,00,000/- had high level of adoption. In contrast, maximum number of the farmers (45.31%) who earned Rs. 1,00, 000 to 2,00,000/- had low level of adoption. Mass media exposure and adoption of solar energy system was found highly significantly associated. Further, results highlight that 56.61 per cent farmers belonged to high mass media exposure had high level of adoption. In comparison, 39.34 per cent farmers belonged to low mass media exposure had low level of adoption. Socio-economic status and adoption of solar energy system was found highly significantly associated. Further, results highlight that 47.96 per cent farmers related to high level of socio-economic status had high level of adoption. In comparison, 47.56 per cent farmers related to low socio-economic status had low level of adoption.

Table 8*Association between Socio-economic Variables and Adoption of Solar Energy (n=240)*

Socio-economic variables	Level of adoption			Total
	Low	Moderate	High	
Age group 30-45 years	34(29.84)	40(35.08)	40(35.08)	114(47.50)
45-60 years	21(28.76)	25(34.24)	27(37.00)	73(30.42)
Above 60 years	18(33.96)	18(33.96)	17(32.08)	53(22.08)
Total	73(30.42)	83(34.58)	84(35.00)	240 (100.00)
df=4		C=0.047		χ^2 Cal=0.526
Caste				
General	41(34.45)	38(31.93)	40(33.61)	119(49.58)
Backward	22(25.58)	37(43.02)	27(31.40)	86(35.83)
Scheduled	10(28.57)	8(22.85)	17(48.58)	35(14.59)
df=4		C=0.168		χ^2 Cal=6.969
Level of education				
Illiterate	10(55.56)	5(27.78)	3(16.66)	18(07.50)
Primary school	14(43.76)	11(34.37)	7(21.87)	32(13.34)
Middle school	17(42.50)	14(35.00)	9(22.50)	40(16.67)
Secondary school	14(23.72)	23(39.00)	22(37.28)	59(24.58)
Senior secondary school	13(19.40)	22(32.83)	32(47.77)	67(27.91)
Graduation or above	5(20.84)	8(33.33)	11(45.84)	24(10.00)
df=10		C=0.287		χ^2 Cal=21.538*
Subsidiary occupation				
No subsidiary occupation	39(28.46)	53(38.68)	45(32.86)	137(57.08)
Business and jobs	19(30.64)	18(29.03)	25(40.33)	62(25.84)
Small scale enterprise	15(36.58)	12(29.26)	14(34.16)	41(17.08)
df=4		C=0.110		χ^2 Cal=2.93
Size of land holding (acre)				
Land less	30(42.85)	25(35.71)	15(21.44)	70(29.16)
Marginal (up to 2.5)	28(37.33)	23(30.66)	24(32.00)	75(31.25)
Small (2.5- 5.0)	11(15.95)	26(37.68)	32(46.37)	69(28.75)
Semi-medium (5.0-10.0)	4(15.38)	9(34.62)	13(50.00)	26(10.84)
df=		C=0.278		χ^2 Cal=20.075**
Type of family				
Nuclear	45(43.28)	22(21.55)	37(35.57)	104(43.34)
Joint	28(20.58)	61(44.85)	47(34.57)	136(56.66)
df=2		C=0.274		χ^2 Cal=19.55**
Size of family				
Up to 4 members	30(44.13)	11(16.17)	27(39.70)	68(28.34)
5-8 members	25(19.70)	62(48.81)	40(31.49)	127(52.91)
Above 8 members	18(40.00)	10(22.23)	17(37.77)	45(18.75)
df=4		C=0.320		χ^2 Cal=27.43**
Annual family income (Rs.)				
1,00,000-2,00,000/-	29(45.31)	13(20.31)	22(34.38)	64(26.67)
2,00,000-3,00,000/-	20(27.40)	35(47.94)	18(24.66)	73(30.42)
3,00,001-4,00,000/-	17(26.15)	22(33.85)	26(40.00)	65(27.08)
Above 4,00,000/-	7(18.42)	13(34.21)	18(47.37)	38(15.83)
df=6		C=0.271		χ^2 Cal=18.986**
Social participation				
No participation	38(33.34)	37(32.45)	39(34.21)	114(47.50)
Member of one organisation	16(28.07)	23(40.35)	18(31.58)	57(23.75)
Member of more than one organisation	19(27.53)	23(33.34)	27(39.13)	69(28.75)
df=4		C=0.088		χ^2 Cal=1.886
Mass media exposure				
Low (up to 10)	48(39.34)	44(36.06)	30(24.60)	122(50.83)
Medium (10-18)	19(29.23)	22(33.84)	24(36.93)	65(27.08)

High (18-24)	6(11.32)	17(32.07)	30(56.61)	53(22.09)
df=4		C=0.282		χ^2 Cal=20.678**
Socio-economic status				
Low (12-18)	39(47.56)	23(28.04)	20(24.40)	82(34.16)
Medium (18-24)	22(25.90)	34(40.00)	29(34.10)	85(35.41)
High (24-30)	12(16.43)	26(35.61)	35(47.96)	73(30.43)
df=4		C=0.284		χ^2 Cal=21.095**

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Significant at 5% level of significance, **Highly significant at 1% level of significance

Figure 3

Socio-economic Variables and Adoption of Solar Energy Penal in Agriculture

Reasons for Adoption of Solar Energy Technology Penal in Agriculture

A perusal of data highlight in table 9 that overwhelming majority of

the farmers (81.25%) adopted solar alternatives due to rising cost of diesel (Rank I) followed by solar systems reduce dependency on unreliable power supply (76.25% agreed, Rank II) and solar energy ensures timely irrigation in remote areas (70.41% agreed, Rank III). Other prominent reasons included reliable availability of sunlight (59.17%, WMS = 2.41) and environmental benefits (56.25%, WMS = 2.40), ranking fourth and fifth respectively. Government subsidies (51.67%) and inspiration from peer success stories (51.25%) also played a considerable role. However, 31.67 per cent farmers agreed with access to credit emerged as least influential factor (Rank X). The overall mean score of 2.35 reflects a generally favourable attitude toward adopting solar energy. The present findings are supported by Sharma and Yadav (2021) who observed that increasing diesel prices, irregular electricity supply and the need for timely irrigation were the major motivating factors behind adoption of solar energy technologies among farmers. The study further revealed that environmental sustainability and government subsidy schemes significantly encouraged positive attitudes towards solar energy adoption in agriculture.

Table 9

Reasons for Adoption of Solar Energy Technology among Farmers (n=240)

Reasons for adoption	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	TWS	WMS	Rank
Rising diesel costs push farmers toward solar	195(81.25)	27(11.25)	18(07.50)	657	2.73*	I
Solar systems reduce power supply dependency	183(76.25)	35(14.58)	22(09.17)	641	2.67*	II
Solar ensures timely irrigation in remote areas	169(70.41)	43(17.91)	28(11.68)	621	2.58*	III
Reliable sunlight makes solar suitable for farmers	142(59.17)	56(23.33)	42(17.50)	580	2.41*	IV
Environmental concerns influence some adopters	135(56.25)	66(27.50)	39(16.25)	576	2.40*	V
Government subsidies encourage solar adoption	124(51.67)	78(32.50)	38(15.83)	566	2.35*	VI
Peer success stories inspire adoption decisions	123(51.25)	72(30.00)	45(18.75)	558	2.32	VII
Low maintenance attracts farmers to solar	89(37.08)	105(43.75)	46(19.17)	523	2.17	VIII
Extension officers promote solar awareness locally	112(46.67)	52(21.67)	76(31.66)	516	2.15	IX
Access to credit enables solar investment	76(31.67)	30(12.50)	134(55.83)	422	1.75	X
Overall Mean Score: 2.35						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Socio-economic Impact of Solar Energy

The data indicate in table 10 that maximum number of the farmers (47.50%) improved in household assets and agricultural tools due to adoption of solar energy system (Rank I) followed by an enhancement in quality of life (49.17%, Rank II) and youth interest in farming innovations (45.83%, Rank III). Other aspects such as

community trust and reduction in conflict over power supply also showed positive trends (38.34%, Rank IV and 40.42%, Rank V). The overall social impact mean score of 1.92 suggests a marginal improvement in social dimensions due to solar adoption.

The economic impact shows a stronger positive effect in table 10. Analysis revealed that 75.83 per cent farmers reported the reduction

in dependence on conventional electricity due to adoption of solar energy (Rank I) and lower input costs leading to higher farm income (62.91%, Rank II). Additionally, economic strengthening of small farmers (68.34%, Rank III) and cost savings on diesel (56.25%, Rank IV) highlight tangible financial benefits of solar technology. The overall economic mean score of 2.20 reflects a moderate to high positive impact of farmers post solar adoption. The findings of the

present study are supported by Meena and Sharma (2022) who reported that adoption of solar energy technologies significantly reduced farmers' dependence on conventional electricity and diesel, resulting in lower irrigation costs and improvement in farm income. The study further highlighted that solar energy strengthened the economic condition of small and marginal farmers by promoting cost-efficient and sustainable agricultural practices.

Table 10*Socio-economic Impact of Solar Energy on Farmers (n=240)*

Socio-economic impact	Increased	Neutral	Decreased	TWS	WMS	Rank
Social impact						
Household assets and agricultural tools	114(47.50)	92(38.34)	34(14.16)	560	2.32*	I
Quality of life	118(49.17)	67(27.91)	55(22.92)	543	2.26*	II
Youth show more interest in farming innovations	110(45.83)	77(32.08)	53(22.09)	537	2.23*	III
Community trust in solar users has grown	92(38.34)	77(32.08)	71(29.58)	501	2.08*	IV
Solar use reduces conflict over power supply	97(40.42)	65(27.08)	78(32.50)	499	2.07*	V
Expenditure on social ceremonies	42(17.50)	142(59.17)	56(23.33)	466	1.94*	VI
Solar energy strengthens farmers' voice in village matters	35(14.58)	155(64.58)	50(20.84)	465	1.93*	VII
Shared solar use promotes community cooperation	52(21.67)	78(32.50)	110(45.83)	422	1.76	VIII
Farmers gain respect for adopting solar energy technology	56(23.34)	69(28.75)	115(47.91)	421	1.75	IX
Solar energy increases farmers' social status locally	57(23.75)	65(27.08)	118(49.17)	419	1.74	X
Education and skill development	45(18.75)	82(34.16)	113(47.09)	412	1.71	XI
Social mobility	44(18.34)	63(26.25)	133(55.41)	391	1.62	XII
Solar adoption improves farmers' public image	38(15.83)	71(29.58)	131(54.59)	387	1.61	XIII
Overall Mean Score: 1.92						
Economic impact						
Solar energy reduces farmers' dependence on electricity	182(75.83)	45(18.75)	13(05.42)	649	2.70*	I
Lower input costs improve overall farm income	151(62.91)	53(22.08)	36(15.00)	648	2.69*	II
Access to solar technology strengthens small farmers economically	164(68.34)	55(22.91)	21(08.75)	623	2.59*	III
Farmers save money previously spent on diesel	135(56.25)	77(32.08)	28(11.67)	587	2.44*	IV
Solar use increases timely irrigation and crop yield	82(34.17)	73(30.41)	85(35.42)	477	1.98	V
Women participate more in solar-based farm activities	75(31.26)	82(34.16)	83(34.58)	472	1.96	VI
Solar energy creates new employment in rural areas	65(27.08)	70(29.16)	105(43.76)	440	1.83	VII
Solar farming encourages investment in modern techniques	53(22.08)	91(37.92)	96(40.00)	437	1.82	VIII
Income stability from solar reduces seasonal migration	56(23.34)	84(35.00)	100(41.66)	436	1.81	IX
Overall Mean Score: 2.20						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Table 11*Constraints Faced by Farmers in Solar Energy Technology (n=240)*

Constraints faced by adopters	Very Serious	Serious	Somewhat Serious	TWS	WMS	Rank
Difficulty in accessing trusted solar vendors	152(63.34)	63(26.25)	25(10.41)	607	2.52*	I
Local electricians not trained in solar technology	134(55.84)	58(24.16)	48(20.00)	566	2.35*	II
No reliable service support after installation	126(52.50)	61(25.41)	53(22.09)	553	2.30*	III
Lack technical knowledge about solar system installation	94(39.16)	78(32.50)	68(28.34)	506	2.10*	IV
Government subsidy procedures are slow and unclear	102(42.50)	57(23.75)	81(33.75)	501	2.08*	V
Unsure about solar system durability	74(30.83)	91(37.91)	75(31.25)	479	1.99	VI
Fear of theft or damage in fields	55(22.91)	71(29.58)	114(47.50)	421	1.75	VII
High initial cost discourages from adopting solar energy	55(22.91)	50(20.83)	135(56.25)	400	1.66	VIII
Inadequate land or space for solar panels	42(17.50)	51(21.25)	147(61.25)	375	1.56	IX
Overall Mean Score: 2.03						

Note. Figures in parentheses denote percentage, *Indicates more than overall mean score, Multiple responses

Constraints Faced by Farmers in Solar Energy Penal

More than three-fifth of the farmers (63.34%) reported difficulty was found in accessing trusted solar vendors as a very serious issue (Rank I) followed by lack of trained local electricians (55.84%, Rank II) and the absence of reliable service support post-installation (52.50%, Rank III). Other notable concerns included insufficient technical knowledge (39.16%, Rank IV) and delays or lack of clarity in government subsidy procedures (42.50%, Rank V). The overall mean score of 2.03 suggests that while farmers face several critical barriers due to growing adoption. The present findings are supported by Rani and Kumar (2021), who reported that lack of reliable technical support, inadequate availability of trained technicians and procedural complications in government subsidy schemes were major constraints faced by farmers in adopting solar energy technologies. The study further revealed that poor after-sale service and limited awareness regarding maintenance practices negatively affected the effective utilization of solar systems in rural agricultural areas.

Conclusion

The study concluded that solar energy has emerged as an effective and sustainable alternative source of energy in agriculture among farmers of Haryana. The findings revealed that majority of the farmers possessed high knowledge (43.75%) and moderate to high adoption levels (69.58%) regarding solar energy technologies. Farmers adopted solar systems mainly due to rising diesel costs, unreliable electricity supply and timely irrigation needs. Solar energy significantly reduced dependence on conventional electricity, lowered irrigation and input costs and improved farm income and household assets. Education, landholding, annual income, mass media exposure and socio-economic status were found significantly associated with knowledge and adoption levels of solar energy. The study further highlighted that solar technology positively influenced the quality of life, economic strengthening of small farmers and sustainable agricultural development in rural areas. However, lack of trained technicians, inadequate service support and delays in subsidy procedures remained major constraints in effective adoption. Therefore, the study suggests

strengthening extension services, improving technical training facilities and simplifying subsidy mechanisms to promote wider adoption of solar energy in agriculture.

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